

The **first** trans-continental **Networking Academy** for **African and European Digital Innovation Hubs.**

D1.5 Data Management Plan – Year 2

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101016687.

Document details

Project Acronym/ Name:	AfriConEU
Project URL:	www.africoneu.eu
Project Type:	Innovation Action (IA)
EU CALL:	H2020-ICT-2018-20 (Information and Communication Technologies)
Grant Agreement No.:	101016687
Project Start Date:	February 2021
Project End Date:	January 2024
Workpackage:	WP1 Project Management
Deliverable:	Data Management Plan – Year 2
Due date of Deliverable:	31/07/2022
Actual Submission Date:	01/08/2022
Name of Lead Beneficiary for this deliverable:	Report Author(s): Tânia Moreira, Ana Aleixo (INOVA+)
Revision:	2.0
Dissemination Level:	Public

Document History			
Version	Date	Comment	Modifications made by
1.0	15.07.2022	First draft shared for review and comments	Tânia Moreira, Ana Aleixo (INOVA+)
2.0	01.08.2022	Final version	Tânia Moreira (INOVA+)

Disclaimer

Any dissemination of results reflects only the author's view and the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Copyright message

© Partners of the AfriConEU Consortium, 2021

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both. Reproduction is authorized provided the source is acknowledged.

Acknowledgements

This deliverable was developed based on collective efforts from all partners of the AfriConEU consortium.

Glossary and Abbreviations	
DM	Dissemination Manager
DMP	Data Management Plan
EC	European Commission
PC	Project Coordinator
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

Table of Contents

Executive Summary	5
1. Introduction.....	6
1.1. About AfriConEU.....	6
1.2. Objectives of D1.5.....	6
1.3. Targets of D1.5.....	6
1.4. Methodology	7
2. Data Summary	8
3. FAIR Data	12
3.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata.....	12
3.2. Making data openly accessible.....	12
3.3. Making data interoperable.....	12
3.4. Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences).....	13
4. Allocation of resources.....	16
5. Data security.....	17
6. Ethical issues.....	18
6.1. General Data Protection Regulation.....	18
6.2. Sensitive Data	18
ANNEXES	20
Annex 1: Informed Consent used to monitor and assess AfriConEU Networking Academy activities	20

List of Tables

Table 1 - Overview on data generated by AfriConEU: primary and secondary	9
Table 2 - Key data licenses to be used by AfriConEU.....	13
Table 3 - Access, interoperability and re-use of AfriConEU data.....	13
Table 4 - Members of the Ethics Board.....	16
Table 5 - Consent and Accessibility of sensitive data generated by AfriConEU	19

Executive Summary

This deliverable was developed in the context of WP1 and intends to be an updated version of *D1.4 - Data Management Plan – Year 1*, which was produced at the beginning of the project (M3). **It integrates the contents from D1.4 and, for this reason, shall replace D1.4.** It aims at supporting partners in the secure and effective use and management of the research data collected and generated within the AfriConEU project. It includes information concerning types of data generated by the project, accessibility, licensing, re-use, allocation of resources, security and ethical issues.

It will be revised by Month 30 to reflect the evolving activities and needs of the project implementation, as well as to achieve a sound data management throughout.

1. Introduction

1.1. About AfriConEU

The AfriConEU project was created with the intent to reinforce, foster, enable and strengthen the digital innovation ecosystems in Africa through international partnerships and collaborations by targeting DIHs in selected African and European countries to build a meaningful network of people to ensure the growth and a thriving digital innovation ecosystem in both continents.

The main goal of the project is to develop, test, and validate the “AfriConEU Networking Academy”, an innovative mechanism for connecting and sharing best practices, experiences, and resources between DIHs in Africa and between DIHs in Africa and the EU, in a comprehensive, replicable, and self-sustaining way. Through two flagship programmes — “Capacity Building” and “Transcontinental Partnership Development” —, the AfriConEU Networking Academy intends to empower and enable African DIHs to best serve their local industry, boost their startup ecosystem and empower the youth population with the necessary skills to thrive in a digitalized world.

1.2. Objectives of D1.5

This deliverable was developed in the context of WP1 and intends to be an updated version of *D1.4 - Data Management Plan – Year 1*, which was produced at the beginning of the project (M3). **It integrates the contents from D1.4 and, for this reason, shall replace D1.4.** It aims at supporting partners in the secure and effective use and management of the research data collected and generated within the AfriConEU project. It presents the types of research data that will be generated or collected during the project, the standards that will be used, how the research data will be preserved and what parts of the datasets will be shared for verification or reuse. Importantly, AfriConEU empirical research will generate data from the quantitative surveys, interviews to relevant stakeholders, focus groups, roundtables and workshops. The qualitative research data will not be made openly accessible as primary data but in a processed form as reports.

1.3. Targets of D1.5

This deliverable is addressed mainly to the AfriConEU consortium partners, aiming at offering them a set of best practice procedures that will ensure a smooth and efficient data management.

1.4. Methodology

The DMP results from a jointly work of AfriConEU partners. It intends to be a supportive document to the project partners. It will be revised by Month 30 to reflect the evolving activities and needs of the project implementation, as well as to achieve a sound data management throughout.

This document follows the structure of “Horizon Europe - Data Management Plan Template” (version 1.0, 05 May 2021) provided by EC and available at <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/how-to-participate/reference-documents;programCode=HORIZON>

2. Data Summary

The AfriConEU foresees several activities of data collection which is essential to achieve the project objectives. Table 1 presents the data type, the activity originating the data, the associate WP in which the activity takes place and the format in which the data will be likely stored. The table not only presents primary data that will be generated by the project, but also secondary data. The AfriConEU project entails activities that will require accessing to secondary data, namely EU-wide available on a variety of sources, including EUROSTAT. In fact, partners will review the literature (studies, blog postings, white papers, consultancy reports etc.) focusing on Africa's tech hubs, and about existing initiatives and programmes focused on strengthening DIHs capacities both in Africa and in Europe. This collection will be essential to develop the *D2.2 Online data base with DIHs Capacity Building programmes* and the *D3.4 Inventory of capacity building resources and ready to use training material*, which are meant to be made available online in a searchable format to facilitate reuse.

Table 1 - Overview on data generated by AfriConEU: primary and secondary

Data	Type	WP	Storage format	Description	Purpose
Primary data					
Stakeholders contacts lists	Text, contacts	2,3,4,5,6	.xls + .docx	The data contain information on the project stakeholders (e.g., representatives of Digital Innovation Hubs, Tech Hubs, Business Incubator Networks, Co-working Spaces, Accelerators, Local entrepreneurial and Startup community supporters, Entrepreneurs, etc). The contact information that is collected includes the name, institutional affiliation, position, email address and office location. <i>[Data collection timeframe: throughout project lifetime]</i>	The project is creating different lists of stakeholders: [WP2] lists used for contacting the project stakeholders to engage on the empirical research activities. [WP3] lists used for contacting stakeholders to engage on workshops to design Flagship Programmes; [WP4] lists of stakeholders that attended project activities and used to contact them for impact assessment purposes; [WP5] list of stakeholders part of the community of practice; [WP6] list of stakeholders that subscribed the project newsletter and that are contacted when newsletters are released.
Photos and/or video collection	Image / video	2, 3, 4, 6	.jpeg + .mp4	Photos and/ video recordings from activities organised or attended by AfriConEU partners. <i>[Data collection timeframe: throughout project lifetime]</i>	The materials collected are used to monitor and promote the project activities, as well as to share relevant knowledge with the wide community (as it is the case of the AfriConEU Networking Academy activities).
Interview data collection [D2.1]	Text + audio	2	.docx + .txt + .mp3	The data consists of written notes from 60 virtual semi-structured one-to-one interviews with hub leaders and managers, entrepreneurs, investors, ecosystem builders and network organisations. <i>[Data collection timeframe: Mar to July 2021]</i>	The collection was used to identify existing challenges and needs for strengthening local DIHs, as well as exploring existing initiatives and programmes focused on enforcing DIHs. Findings contributed to the definition of the project Flagship Programmes.
Roundtable data collection – state of play [D2.1]	Text + audio	2	.mp3 + .docx + .txt	The data consists of written notes and summaries from four virtual ecosystem roundtables hosted by ATBN in partnership with local DIH partners of the AfriConEU project including HapaSpace (Ghana), Emerging Communities Africa (Nigeria), Buni Hub (Tanzania) and Outbox (Uganda). <i>[Data collection timeframe: May to June 2021]</i>	The collection was used to provide insights about the maturity level and the needs of the local ecosystems to influence the development of the AfriConEU Networking Academy programmes, with special focus on transcontinental partnerships building.
Online survey data –	Text + numerical	2	.xls + .csv	The data contains answers 266 diverse stakeholders, including African entrepreneurs, and	The collection was used to identify existing challenges and needs for strengthening local DIHs, including at the level of

Data	Type	WP	Storage format	Description	Purpose
stakeholders' needs and interests [D2.1]				32 hub leaders. The survey was run as an online questionnaire. <i>[Data collection timeframe: Feb 2021 to July 2021]</i>	capacity building. It contributed to the definition of the project Flagship Programmes.
Online survey data – lessons and interests for DIHs capacity building programmes [D2.3]	Text + numerical	2	.xls + .csv	The data gathers the answers from 182 organisations (DIHs helpers, DIHs). <i>[Data collection timeframe: Mar to Aug 2021]</i>	The data collected was used to know more about existing capacity building programmes and DIH's interests. This information was used to define the project Flagship Programmes.
Roundtable data collection [D2.4]	Text + audio	2	.mp3 + .docx + .txt	The data consists of protocols, recordings, notes and summaries from 4 roundtables bringing together 94 participants representatives from DIHs from Europe and Africa. <i>[Data collection timeframe: Sep to Nov 2021]</i>	The collection was used to identify current perceptions towards cross-continental and intracontinental partnerships and define needs and preferences. It will influence the development of the Trans-Continental Partnership Development Flagship Programme.
Workshop data collection [D3.6]	Text + audio	3	.mp3 + .docx + .txt	The data consists of protocols, recordings, notes and summaries from online international participative workshop bringing together representatives from DIHs from Europe and Africa. <i>[Data collection timeframe: Feb 2022]</i>	The data collected was used to define the objectives, thematic areas, methods and tools of the Trans-continental Partnerships Building Flagship Programme.
Online survey data – monitoring & assessment	Text + numerical	4	.xls + .csv	The data contain protocols and answers from speakers, attendees and activities organisers assessing each AfriConEU Networking Academy activity performance. <i>[Data collection timeframe: May 2022 to Oct 2023]</i>	The data collected will be used to monitor and enhance the Networking Academy activities.
Interviews – success stories	Text + audio + video + image	4	.docx + .mp3 + .mp4 + .jpeg	The data will contain protocols and answers from selected success stories (representative of DIH, start-ups, etc.).	The data will be used to engage the community, raise awareness on successful and inspiring stories and motivate peer learning.

Data	Type	WP	Storage format	Description	Purpose
Design Thinking Bootcamps data	Text + numerical	4	.docx + .xls	The data will contain protocols, written notes and summaries done at the 4 design thinking bootcamps to be organised in each one of the targeted African countries, and addressing digital ecosystem stakeholders and experts from Europe and Africa. <i>[Data collection timeframe: July 2023]</i>	The collection will be used to support the ideation for joint programme development between EU-AU actors.
Secondary Data					
Literature Review data [D2.1]	Text	2	.docx	The data gathered was obtained from several sources including, government policies, NGO and international NGO reports, newspaper articles, academic journals, and blogs. <i>[Data collection timeframe: Feb to July 2021]</i>	The literature review supported the contextualisation of the project activities. The information obtained was used to write the Country Snapshot of this report. It provided insight into the tech and innovation ecosystems of the four countries that are at the centre of the project – Nigeria, Uganda, Ghana and Tanzania.
Database DIH's Capacity Building Programmes [D2.2]	Text	2	.docx	Data gathering the mapping of DIH's helpers and list of existing capacity building programmes for DIH. <i>[Data collection timeframe: Mar to Aug 2021]</i>	This mapping is used not only to share relevant information with stakeholders, but also to design the AfriConEU Capacity Building Flagship Programme activities.

3. FAIR Data

Following the guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020¹, the next sub-sections present the main considerations of AfriConEU partners to ensure proper sharing and management of the data collected.

3.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Data and project results will be shared with the relevant communities through publications as well as through open access data repositories. An important aspect for making data findable is to attribute a suitable naming convention to project data.

In this sense, datasets generated during the project will use a name convention as follows: **AfriConEU_WPxx_TXx_DDMMYYYY_.doc**, i.e. acronym of the project + WP generating the dataset + Task generating the dataset + data of creation with format DDMMYYYY + dataset format. As for project reports/deliverables, name segments should be as follows: **AfriConEU_D1.1_15032021_V01.doc** – meaning that the report consist on Version 1 of the Deliverable D1.1 produced on 15 March 2021.

The AfriConEU metadata will be in a standard format and will include all the following: i) the terms “European Union (EU)” and “Horizon 2020”; ii) the name of the action, acronym and grant number; iii) the publication date, and length of embargo period if applicable, and iv) a persistent identifier.

3.2. Making data openly accessible

AfriConEU participates in the Pilot on Open Research Data in Horizon 2020 and will therefore offer open access to data generated, as well as to relevant publications and reports produced throughout the project lifetime.

In addition to the project SharePoint, which is password-protected and only accessible by partners, relevant datasets will be also stored in ZENODO (<https://zenodo.org>) - the open access repository of OpenAIRE, the Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe (<https://www.openaire.eu>).

3.3. Making data interoperable

The data produced and/or used in the project should be interoperable allowing data exchange between researchers, institutions, organisations, countries, etc. Interoperability will be supported by using standard metadata and file formats.

¹ https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-data-mgt_en.pdf

3.4. Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)

Public data will be made available for re-use. Data will be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible when no limitations are identified by the key stakeholders. Two Creative Commons licenses will mainly used:

Table 2 - Key data licenses to be used by AfriConEU

	The user is free to:	Under the following terms:
<p>CC BY-NC-ND 4.0: Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivatives 4.0 International. [URL]</p>	<p>Share — copy and redistribute the material in any medium or format</p>	<p>Attribution — You must give appropriate credit, provide a link to the license, and indicate if changes were made. You may do so in any reasonable manner, but not in any way that suggests the licensor endorses you or your use.</p> <p>NonCommercial — You may not use the material for commercial purposes.</p> <p>NoDerivatives — If you remix, transform, or build upon the material, you may not distribute the modified material.</p> <p>No additional restrictions — You may not apply legal terms or technological measures that legally restrict others from doing anything the license permits.</p>
<p>CC BY 4.0: Attribution 4.0 International [URL]</p>	<p>Share — copy and redistribute the material in any medium or format</p> <p>Adapt — remix, transform, and build upon the material for any purpose, even commercially.</p>	<p>Attribution — You must give appropriate credit, provide a link to the license, and indicate if changes were made. You may do so in any reasonable manner, but not in any way that suggests the licensor endorses you or your use.</p>

Table 3 provides details for each type of data generated by the project concerning its accessibility, interoperability and re-use.

Table 3 - Access, interoperability and re-use of AfriConEU data

Data	Access	Interoperability	Re-use
Primary data			
Stakeholders contacts lists	Non-public. The lists gather sensitive data (e.g. names, contacts). It will must remain private and for AfriConEU partners use only.	Not allowed. The lists will not be made publicly available.	Not allowed. The lists will not be made publicly available.
Photos and/ or video collection	Accessible in project website, social media and other platforms.	Not allowed. The data is not suitable for interoperability.	CC BY-NC-ND 4.0: Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs

Data	Access	Interoperability	Re-use
Interview data collection	<p>Conclusions gathered in reports (D2.1) to be accessible in project website, social media and other platforms.</p> <p>Primary data accessible by contacting main authors. Data must be shared after anonymised process.</p>	Interoperability ensured by commonly known research language.	CC BY 4.0: Attribution
Roundtable data collection – state of play	<p>Conclusions gathered in reports (D2.1) to be accessible in project website, social media and other platforms.</p> <p>Primary data accessible by contacting main authors. Data must be shared after anonymised process.</p>	Interoperability ensured by commonly known research language.	CC BY 4.0: Attribution
Online survey data – stakeholders’ needs and interests	<p>Conclusions gathered in reports (D2.1) to be accessible in project website, social media and other platforms.</p> <p>Primary data accessible by contacting main authors. Data must be shared after anonymised process.</p>	Interoperability ensured by commonly known research language.	CC BY 4.0: Attribution
Online survey data – lessons and interests for DIHs capacity building programmes	<p>Conclusions gathered in reports (D2.3) to be accessible in project website, social media and other platforms.</p> <p>Primary data accessible by contacting main authors. Data must be shared after anonymised process.</p>	Interoperability ensured by commonly known research language.	CC BY 4.0: Attribution
Roundtable data collection	<p>Conclusions gathered in reports (D2.4) to be accessible in project website, social media and other platforms.</p> <p>Primary data accessible by contacting main authors.</p>	Interoperability ensured by commonly known research language.	CC BY 4.0: Attribution
Workshop data collection	<p>Conclusions gathered in reports (D3.6) to be accessible in project website, social media and other platforms.</p> <p>Primary data accessible by contacting main authors. Data must be shared after anonymised process.</p>	Interoperability ensured by commonly known research language.	CC BY 4.0: Attribution

Data	Access	Interoperability	Re-use
Online survey data – monitoring & assessment	Conclusions gathered in reports to be accessible in project website, social media and other platforms. Primary data accessible by contacting main authors. Data must be shared after anonymised process.	Interoperability ensured by commonly known research language.	CC BY 4.0: Attribution
Interviews – success stories	Accessible in project website, social media and other platforms.	Not allowed. The data is not suitable for interoperability.	CC BY-NC-ND 4.0: Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs
Design Thinking Bootcamps data	Conclusions gathered in reports to be accessible in project website, social media and other platforms. Primary data accessible by contacting main authors.	Interoperability ensured by commonly known research language.	CC BY 4.0: Attribution
Secondary Data			
Literature Review data	Conclusions gathered in reports (D2.1) to be accessible in project website, social media and other platforms.	Interoperability ensured by commonly known research language.	CC BY 4.0: Attribution
Database DIH's Capacity Building Programmes	Conclusions gathered in reports (D2.2) to be accessible in project website, social media and other platforms.	Interoperability ensured by commonly known research language.	CC BY 4.0: Attribution

4. Allocation of resources

In compliance with the Data Protection Directive 95/46/EC and with Article 29 Working Party 8/2010 opinion, a Data Controller is appointed as part of WP1 – Pedro Castro (INOVA+), responsible to the project coordinator and having the appropriate local registration; other partners will act as Data Processors in connection with their specific responsibilities and tasks.

The consortium includes an Ethics Board made up of the coordinator and one member from each partner (Table 3). All issues pertaining to ethics approval will be forwarded to the Ethics Board for notification and approval.

Table 4 - Members of the Ethics Board

Partner	Representative of the Partner	Partner	Representative of the Partner
INOVA+	Miguel Sousa	STMLI	Irene Kalemaki
ECA	Peace Odili	ITC	Sasa Straus
YMH	Marilena Maragkou	BUNI	Edwin Bakalemwa
PBS	Catarina Reis	ATBN	Eunice Ball
OUTBOX	Richard Zulu	HAPA	Douglas Boateng
DPIXEL	Stefano Azzalin		

By concerning the whole project, data management will be of the responsibility of partners according to their specific responsibilities and tasks, but particularly of the Project Coordinator (as Data Controller), the Work Package Leaders who are responsible to ensure the implementation of the data management procedures in their respective WP, and of the Dissemination Manager who shall monitor that publications produced by the project are clearly identified and assist and advice partners on diffusion paths.

5. Data security

To ensure the security of the data, the following procedures shall be followed by members of the AfriConEU consortium:

- ✓ Store data in at least two separate locations to avoid loss of data;
- ✓ Perform regular and appropriate backups to avoid loss of data;
- ✓ Encrypt data if it is deemed necessary by the participating researchers;
- ✓ Label files in a systematically structured way in order to ensure the coherence of the final dataset (as described in 2.1).
- ✓ Limit the use of USB flash drives.

Data is to be stored in the project SharePoint on MSTeams which is password-protected and only accessible by partners. Data stored on SharePoint will be kept for 5 years after the end of the project and made available for third parties upon request. Data shared through ZENODO will be available according to the repository access rules.

6. Ethical issues

AfriConEU project and all those involved from beneficiary and partner organisations will conduct research and commit to abide strictly to the principles of:

- ✓ Respecting human dignity and integrity;
- ✓ Ensuring honesty and transparency towards participants and notably getting free and informed consent;
- ✓ Protecting vulnerable persons;
- ✓ Ensuring privacy and confidentiality;
- ✓ Sharing the benefits with disadvantaged populations;
- ✓ Following the highest standards of research integrity (i.e. avoiding any kind of fabrication, falsification, plagiarism, unjustified double funding, or other type of research misconduct) as defined in the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity.

6.1. General Data Protection Regulation

AfriConEU will comply with the ethical standards and guidelines of Horizon 2020 regulations that apply to the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), and in accordance with the international and EU Directives/Regulations, as well as respective national iterative.

The AfriConEU Online Community will be designed to facilitate interactions between the project community and its different stakeholders around DIHs and start-ups. Users will be able to interact with like-minded users to exchange knowledge, experiences, contacts, increase their visibility and be supported. They will self-certify during registration that they are adults (18-65) and they will agree with the legal terms and regulations.

6.2. Sensitive Data

Collection of personal data may take place during the various initiatives of the project; the surveys focus groups, interviews, workshops, and the different events. Participants will be given information about how their data will be collected, protected during the project and either destroyed or re-used at the end of the project. In the latter case, they will be reminded that they may withhold such data; and that any such additional activities will remain strictly within the bounds covered by their informed consent form.

Non-professional personal data, if collected, will be stored securely on a password-protected computer, only used for the purpose for which it was collected. If a plan to reuse data is considered, participants will be given information about this as soon as it becomes available and be given the opportunity to consent or withdraw their data.

Table 5 - Consent and Accessibility of sensitive data generated by AfriConEU

Data	Consent	Accessibility of sensitive data
Primary data		
Stakeholders contacts lists	Yes. Stakeholders are requested to read and agreed with consent form. Their contacts are used for the agreed options.	Only accessible by AfriConEU partners.
Photos and/ or video collection	Yes. Stakeholders are requested to read and agreed with consent form. The materials are used for the agreed options.	No sensitive data is shared. Materials are publicly available under restricted license.
Interview data collection	Yes. Stakeholders are requested to read and agreed with consent form. The materials are used for the agreed options.	No sensitive data is shared. Data is shared after anonymization process.
Roundtable data collection – state of play	Yes. Stakeholders are requested to read and agreed with consent form. The materials are used for the agreed options.	No sensitive data is shared. Data is shared after anonymization process.
Online survey data – stakeholders’ needs and interests	Yes. Stakeholders are requested to read and agreed with consent form. The materials are used for the agreed options.	No sensitive data is shared. Data is shared after anonymization process.
Online survey data – lessons and interests for DIHs capacity building programmes	Yes. Stakeholders are requested to read and agreed with consent form. The materials are used for the agreed options.	No sensitive data is shared. Data is shared after anonymization process.
Roundtable data collection	Yes. Stakeholders are requested to read and agreed with consent form. The materials are used for the agreed options.	No sensitive data is shared. Data is shared after anonymization process.
Workshop data collection	Yes. Stakeholders are requested to read and agreed with consent form. The materials are used for the agreed options.	No sensitive data is shared. Data is shared after anonymization process.
Online survey data – monitoring & assessment	Yes. Stakeholders are requested to read and agreed with consent form. The materials are used for the agreed options.	No sensitive data is shared. Data is shared after anonymization process.
Interviews – success stories	Yes. Stakeholders are requested to read and agreed with consent form. The materials are used for the agreed options.	No sensitive data is shared. Materials are publicly available under restricted license.
Design Thinking Bootcamps data	Yes. Stakeholders will be requested to read and agreed with consent form. The materials are used for the agreed options.	No sensitive data will be shared.
Secondary Data		
Literature Review data	Not applicable.	Not applicable.
Database DIH’s Capacity Building Programmes	Not applicable.	Not applicable.

ANNEXES

Annex 1: Informed Consent used to monitor and assess AfriConEU Networking Academy activities

[Activity Title]

Thank you for agreeing to take part in this survey!

The purpose of this survey is to collect your opinion on the event you just attended, its contents and the level of knowledge acquired. This will allow us to point out strengths and weaknesses and improve our actions. Your feedback is relevant and we appreciate the time you dedicate to this survey.

Your responses to this survey are anonymous. Your participation is voluntary and you may withdraw at any time. Your answers will be used solely for the purpose of the internal evaluation process of the AfriConEU project events.

To read more about the data management and the processing of your answers please click here: https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1ichAY4SaoundPO_NKpVSpACk9sKIWgerBMAighREiNs/edit *[text provided below]*

Thank you for your time.

? If you have any question, do not hesitate to contact us: africoneu@inova.business

ABOUT AFRICONEU PROJECT

AfriconEU is the first Trans-continental Networking Academy for African and European Digital Innovation Hubs. As part of the project, a series of capacity building and partnership development events are being organised for empowering African DIHs to best serve their local industry, boost their innovation ecosystem, support the scale up of African start-ups and empower the youth population with the necessary skills to thrive in a digitalized world.

More information: <https://africoneu.eu/>

[information available in the link provided above]

Informed Consent

Before directing you to the survey, we ask for your explicit permission to proceed with the questionnaire and process your answers. For that, we share further information on the AfriConEU project and the survey we are conducting.

ABOUT THE PROJECT AND THE SURVEY

AfriConEU is a project funded by the European Commission's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme. AfriConEU aims at supporting Digital Innovation Hubs in Africa and strengthening a common EU-Africa innovation ecosystem.

This survey is led by Stimuli for Social Change, who is a partner organisation in the AfriConEU project. This survey lasts approximately ten minutes. You will be asked questions about your experience in the AfriConEU event you participated.

YOUR DATA

During this survey we will ask you to provide some personal data such as: Gender, country of residency, job title, work sector and type of organisation you represent.

In this survey we do not ask for your name or email to make sure your answers are hard to be associated to you. We are going to collect your data through this online survey, and use it in statistical and qualitative analyses.

SHARING AND RETAINING OF YOUR DATA

Your data will be kept strictly confidential. We will only share your personal data with people who are directly involved in this research. Additionally, we will make sure that your personal data will be as de-identified/ anonymised as possible during our research, unless you give your consent to be identifiable.

Hopefully this form has informed you sufficiently about us and our research. We greatly appreciate your participation.